

The iPWR MELCOR 2.2 Parametric Sensitivity Analysis

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ABSTRACT

In this paper an integral Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR) accident response was studied. The generic design was developed based on public data for a Small Modular Reactor (SMR) with 160 MWth. The iPWR model was developed with MELCOR 2.2.18 severe accident integral computer code. The scenario of Loss of Coolant Accident (LOCA) with loss of Emergency Core Cooling System (ECCS) was studied for 100'000 seconds. This unlikely sequence can be considered as the unmitigated LOCA and can potentially lead to core degradation and severe accident. A parametric sensitivity analysis for a core related heat transfer parameters was performed to investigate conditions which can lead to core damage. Nine cases were studied by increasing or decreasing heat transfer capabilities, in most cases at the core barrel region. It was observed that in spite of no ECCS, no significant core collapse was observed and only local degradation was present. In all cases intensive exothermic oxidation occurred, mainly at the top part of the core with between 40-60% zirconium oxidized. The passive core cooling mechanism were efficient enough to avoid further accident progression for the considered time interval. It is in contrary to large PWRs, where unmitigated LOCA would lead to total and fast meltdown. This work will be further used in efforts of Uncertainty Quantification for iPWR. It can also facilitate discussion about accident management strategies in iPWR type SMRs.

KEYWORDS

Integral PWR, SMR, severe accident, sensitivity analysis, MELCOR

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1. INTRODUCTION

Small Modular Reactors are currently a important research and development topic. Several dozen designs are being developed all around the world with both Light Water Reactor (LWR) and Non-LWR technologies [1]. The most advanced projects are small LWRs (PWR, BWR), especially integral PWRs, which are likely to be deployed in the near future.

Integral PWRs (iPWR) will have very low Core Damage Frequency [2] due to passive systems, integral design, small power-to-volume ratio and other favorable characteristics. However, understanding their response to accidents with core damage is a research problem worth proper attention. Also, the specific design features of SMR LWRs would eventually affect their response to accident sequences in comparison to large LWRs. Understanding the difference in the phenomenology, and progression of potential severe accidents in SMRs will affect their future safe operation and accident management strategies. It is also a topic of the Horizon Euratom Safety Analysis of SMR with PASSive Mitigation strategies - Severe Accident (SASPAM-SA) project. The research presented in this paper is a part of it [3].

This research is focused on the modeling of a small integral PWR with the MELCOR2.2 computer code. The integral computer code developed by Sandia National Laboratories (SNL) is one of the most popular codes dedicated to severe accidents [6]. In the iPWRs, there are nonstandard features like the passive cooling without pumps, the helical coil Steam Generator (SG), passive decay heat removal system, and coupling between integrated parts of the system: reactor vessel, containment vessel, and a reactor building with a large pool. Recently, developers of MELCOR added several features to facilitate simulation of SMRs, e.g., heat transfer coefficients dedicated to the helical geometry [11,12].

The passive SMR designs like iPWR pose a challenge for integral codes. Specifically, passive phenomena like natural circulation are more demanding in terms of modeling, and integral code users commonly use simplified models because detailed models are challenging computationally. Moreover, physical phenomena related to passive systems and their numerical models can eventually be unstable and sensitive to such simplifications, consequently they can be characterized by higher uncertainty. On the other hand, in severe accident codes simplified models can amplify inaccurate predictions of some phenomena. In effect, sensitivity and uncertainty analysis can be considered of critical importance for passive designs, as it allows deeper understanding of the considered system. Despite all improvements already done by MELCOR developers, the specific features of iPWR could be challenging to accurately simulate natural circulation taking into account the simplification of the numerical models and fully passive design.

This paper presents a preliminary study in the form of parametric sensitivity analysis for the selected core heat transfer parameters in the iPWR generic plant. The attention was put on aspects related to the heat structures around the core and their ability to extract heat in the case of an accident. It is supplemented by the analysis of the accident progression and phenomena, including basic thermal-hydraulics, hydrogen production and core degradation. This work is an introductory step to the support a complete uncertainty quantification analysis of an iPWR design.

2. SASPAM-SA project

Currently, there is a growing interest towards the deployment of SMRs, and several activities are underway in many countries to prepare for possible licensing needs. Despite the reinforcement of the first three levels of the Defence-in-Depth (DiD), a sound demonstration of the ability of the safety systems in an iPWR to respond to transients potentially leading to Severe Accidents (SA) should be carried out (DiD levels 4-5). In this context, the key objective of the SASPAM-SA project is to investigate the applicability and transfer of the knowledge and know-how from operating large-LWR reactors to the near-term deployment of iPWR, in the view of SA and the European needs for licensing analysis of Emergency Planning Zones. The key

outcome of the project is to be supportive of the iPWR licensing process by bringing up key elements of the safety demonstration needed and speeding up the licensing and siting process of iPWRs in Europe. The SASPAM-SA project proposal was funded in HORIZON-EURATOM-2021-NRT-01-01, “Safety of operating nuclear power plants and research reactors”, and it is coordinated by ENEA. Twenty-three organizations from fourteen countries are involved.

In order to maximize the knowledge transferability and impacts of the project, two generic design concepts, characterized by different evolutionary innovations in comparison with larger operating reactors, have been selected for the analyses. These two generic reactor concepts include the main iPWR design features, considered in the most promising designs ready to go on the European market, allowing to assess in a wider way the capability of codes (SA and CFD) to simulate the SA phenomena typical of iPWR. It is not the SASPAM-SA project’s objective to assess the generic reactor designs selected but, based on the project findings, allow a more general statement on the capability of the codes to simulate postulated SA conditions in iPWR [5].

3. PLANT MODEL

3.1. Studied plant

The activity presented here has been developed in the frame of the WP2, “Input deck development and hypothetical SA scenarios assessment (SCENARIOS)” coordinated by KIT, having as a major objective the development of generic but representative iPWR SA code input-decks and the analysis of the iPWR behavior under hypothetical postulated SA conditions. The studied plant is a generic integral Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR) with a thermal power of about 160 MWth (SMR) characterized by a compact Steam Generator (SG) and a submerged containment configuration (in SASPAM-SA called design 1) see Figure 1. The plant specification and design details were developed based on the SASPAM-SA database based on publicly available data [3, 4].

The primary system operates with natural circulation, the pressurizer is integrated with the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV); a helical coil steam generator is inside the downcomer, and the entire RPV is inside the Containment Pressure Vessel (CPV), which is then located in a large Reactor Pool (RP). Thanks to the integral design, LBLOCA events cannot occur in this type of reactors. A SBLOCA passive mitigation strategy is then adopted which relies on primary/containment coupling through reactor venting valves. More details on primary/containment coupling and related experiments, publicly available to the international community, are in [9,10]. A Decay Heat Removal System (DHRS) has been added in the PSI MELCOR nodalization for a potential sensitivity study of the passive condenser.

3.2. MELCOR input deck

The input deck for generic iPWR was developed with MELCOR 2.2.18. State-of-the-Art MELCOR guidelines were utilized as much as possible [11]. The input deck contains 79 Control Volumes (CVH), 116 Flow Paths (FL), 62 Heat Structures (HS), and 256 control systems (CF & TF). The model is divided, similarly as the plant, into three main parts: the RPV, CPV, and the RP, as depicted in Figure 1 and Figure 2. All necessary logic and signals were implemented using Control Functions (CF). For the studied model the radionuclide (RN) package is active. The reference model of the present sensitivity analysis (SA0) uses a new MELCOR eutectic model.

Figure 1. Basic scheme of the iPWR reactor.

3.2.1. Primary side - RPV

The primary side has relatively fine nodalization (Figure 2) when compared to typical MELCOR inputs for Gen-II reactors. The riser, the pressurizer and downcomer have several control volumes, and the level of detail is motivated by the complexity of the natural circulation phenomena, which should be modeled accurately enough, for both steady-state and transient.

The core has six control volumes (CVH package) for the active part and two for the bypass. The COR package model is divided radially into 4 rings and axially into 9 levels. The active core is between axial levels 5-8 and rings 1-3. In the radial ring 4, only levels 2 and 3 are activated, as well as part of the lower plenum.

3.2.2. Steam generator and secondary side

The steam generators consist of two helical coil banks wired around the riser, and located in the downcomer of the primary side (Figure 1). They thermally couple the primary side and the secondary side by 14 heat structures. The shell side of SGs is represented by 14 different CVHs (7 for each coil) as depicted in (Figure 2). The secondary side also covers feedwater, turbine, steam lines, and steam generator shell side. It is also connected with the Decay Heat Removal System (DHRS). The reference model uses the dedicated helical coil model for heat transfer for the tube side and Zukauskas model for shell side of the SG [12, 13].

3.2.3. Engineering Safety Features

The safety systems DHRS and Emergency Core Cooling System (ECCS) are implemented as well. The first, the DHRS, is a heat exchanger connected to helical SGs tube side which transmits heat from the RPV to the RP during accident conditions by the means of natural convection. The second system is the ECCS, the five-valve system designed to allow the natural circulation of water between RPV and CPV during accidents. The ECCS contains three Reactor Ventilation Valves (RVV) placed on the top of RPV and two Reactor Recirculation Valves (RRV), placed slightly above active core. Pressurizer safety valves are also

modeled. All these valves connect RPV with CPV. Schematically, valves are presented in Figure 1 and details are in Figure 2.

Figure 2. MELCOR model of the iPWR. SNAP visualization.

3.2.4. Containment Pressure Vessel, Reactor Pool and the environment

The CPV is modeled with twelve control volumes and several flow paths. Thanks to that it allows to mimic flow patterns inside the vessel and condensation phenomena. It is connected with the RPV by series of ECCS and safety valves (Figure 2) and by HSs. It also accepts the LOCA discharge, as it entirely surrounds the RPV. In this simulation the CPV is assumed without liquid water in subatmospheric pressure.

The reactor pool includes eight control volumes filled with water and connected paths (see Figure 2). It is also connected with the reactor building, which has vent paths to the environment (see also Figure 2) and with CPV via HSs. The pool is the main heat sink, able to extract heat from CPV. The water can be evaporated and heat can be transferred to the environment – the ultimate heat sink.

4. PARAMETRIC SENSITIVITY STUDY

4.1. Studied accident sequence and assumptions

All calculations were initiated with 5000 seconds steady-state. The Postulated Initiating Event (PIE) in this study is the break in the ECCS system – a single valve of the RVV system unintentionally stuck open (or break occurs, causing loss of coolant) releasing steam from the RPV to the CPV. The studied sequence is RVV Loss of Coolant Accident (RVV-LOCA) followed by SCRAM. In order to reach the core degradation or severe accident conditions, additional critical assumptions have been postulated and implemented. The assumption is that the remaining parts of the ECCS do not work – hence, other two RVV cannot open, and what is critical, both recirculation lines (RRV) also do not open. It is also assumed that DHRS system does not work. Discharge of the steam from the RPV to the CPV is possible, but the circulation path of water from CPV to RPV is blocked. The heat removal is substantially degraded. In effect there is no ECCS to the RPV during LOCA, thus no water re-circulate from CPV to RPV. It is equivalent to an unmitigated LOCA sequence with potential for core melt.

4.2. Studied parameters and calculated cases

Selected model parameters responsible for the heat transmission from the core were modified. These were changed to assess if it is possible to eventually reach the core damage conditions. The list of calculated cases with main parameters and short descriptions is presented in Table I and partially discussed in [14]. The reference model is SA0 with best-estimate setup, eutectic model and helical coil model for the SG heat structures. By best-estimate parameters authors mean default parameters suggested in MELCOR manuals [12,13] or MELCOR best practices [11] which were used as a starting point for parametric analyses. This is a preliminary list of parameters, the study of other parameters are considered for future analyses.

All sensitivity cases from SA1-SA10 are based on the SA0 case, which means, if it is not stated differently in Table I, the changes to SA cases are done for a base case (SA0) input deck. The first approach was to modify heat transfer at the shell side of the SG, by changing set of correlations for the convective heat transfer – cases SA0, and SA1 (Table I). Secondly, the core boundary heat structures in contact with bypass CVH were modified to be in the direct contact with core CVHs – SA2. Also a scaling factor was introduced for heat transfer. The third case SA3, includes modification of radiation exchange factors for axial and radial heat transfer in the core. The SA4 is an extension of SA2 by addition of scaling factors for the other side of the core barrel HSs. The SA5 introduces additional heat transfer paths for radiation between external core ring fuel (FU) components and core barrel HS using COR_HTR card – for more details see the manual [12,13]. SA6 is variation of SA5 case by increasing the effective radiation transfer area. The case SA7 changes sides (in SA6) from internal (left) to external (right). SA8 is excluded from the studies as it presents similar assumptions as SA7 and the results were identical. SA9 is based on SA3 but with reduced radiative exchange factors and SA10 is model with turned-off COR eutectic model.

Table I. List of studied cases with description of the applied modifications.

Case	Parameter	Description
SA0	HS_LB	HelicalSG boundary conditions implemented on the internal side of all the SG HS
SA1	HS_LB	CalcCoefHS boundary conditions implemented on the internal side of all the SG HS
SA2	HT_RBT 'xhtfcr'	Heat transfer directly from COR CVHs to downcomer CVHs in contrary to base case SA0

		Increased atmosphere heat transfer scaling factor 'xhtfcr' for external (downcomer) side from 1.0 to 1.5 for the HS responsible for heat transfer from external core to the downcomer CVH
SA3	COR_RF 'fcela' 'fclcr'	Increased: -radiative exchange factor for radiation radially 'fcela' from 0.2 to 0.5 -radiative exchange factor for radiation axially upward 'fclcr' from 0.2 to 0.4
SA4	HT_RBT 'xhtfcr' HT_LBT 'xhtfcl' 'xhtfclr'	Heat transfer directly from COR CVHs to downcomer CVHs in contrary to base case SA0 Increased (extension of SA2) -atmosphere heat transfer scaling factor 'xhtfcr' for external (downcomer) side from 1.0 to 1.5 -atmosphere heat transfer scaling factor 'xhtfcl' and 'xhtfclr' for internal (core) side from 1.0 to 1.5 - radiative heat transfer scaling factor 'xhtfclr' for internal (core) side from 1.0 to 1.5 for the HS responsible for heat transfer from external core to the downcomer CVH
SA5	COR_HTR activated HS_LBR activated	-Additional core heat transfer path between specific components in specific COR package cells. COR_HTR and defined like: <i>COR_HTR 4 !n iafrom irfrom icmp1 iato irto icmp2 htrmdl path</i> <i>1 5 3 FU 102 'LEFT' HS RADIATE-CONST 0.8</i> <i>2 6 3 FU 103 'LEFT' HS RADIATE-CONST 0.8</i> <i>3 7 3 FU 104 'LEFT' HS RADIATE-CONST 0.8</i> <i>4 8 3 FU 105 'LEFT' HS RADIATE-CONST 0.8</i> -HS_LBR activated in HS from core to downcomer and defined like : <i>! emiswr rmodr pathr</i> <i>HS_LBR 1.0 EQUIV-BAND 3.24</i>
SA6	COR_HTR activated HS_LBR Activated	Extension of SA5 'path' parameter increased from 0.8 to 1.7
SA7	COR_HTR activated HS_LBR activated	<i>Description see – SA5</i> <i>COR_HTR 4 !n iafrom irfrom icmp1 iato irto icmp2 htrmdl path</i> <i>1 5 3 FU 102 'RIGHT' HS RADIATE-CONST 1.7</i> <i>2 6 3 FU 103 'RIGHT' HS RADIATE-CONST 1.7</i> <i>3 7 3 FU 104 'RIGHT' HS RADIATE-CONST 1.7</i> <i>4 8 3 FU 105 'RIGHT' HS RADIATE-CONST 1.7</i>
SA9	COR_RF 'fcela' 'fclcr'	Decreased -radiative exchange factor for radiation radially 'fcela' from 0.2 to 0.1 -radiative exchange factor for radiation axially upward 'fclcr' from 0.2 to 0.1
SA10	COR_EUT	Like SA0 but eutectic model was turned-off.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Thermal hydraulics

Studying the primary pressure we can observe that in a very short time it drops from initial 12.7 MPa to 4 MPa due to rapid depressurization and pressure equilibration with the CPV (Figure 3). Then pressure decreases slowly for several hours, due to the cooling of the RPV and the whole CPV. The RPV is constantly discharging steam created by decay heat to CPV and it leads to removal of water from the RPV and its water level decreases.

Figure 3. Left - Pressure in the primary system. Right - Pressure in the CPV.

During the initial blowdown, water level rapidly drops to $\sim +8.5\text{m}$ (0.0m is bottom of the lower plenum), then slowly decreases with a much lower rate (Figure 4). It is approaching the Top of Active Fuel (TAF) in about 5h after the PIE. Half of the core is reached at $\sim 8\text{h}$, and it takes 20-22 hours to fully uncover the core.

Figure 4. Water level (collapsed) in the core. Red area – active core. Bottom of Active Fuel (BAF) at +1.3m and Top of Active Fuel (TAF) at +3.3m.

5.2. Oxidation and core degradation

When the half of the core is uncovered at $\sim 8\text{h}$ (Figure 4), the temperature starts to increase (Figure 5). It leads to the oxidation, partial core degradation, and consequent pressure increase observed in the RPV and CPV (Figure 3). Pressure rise is due to the non-condensable hydrogen gas, which can be a significant source of pressure in addition to the steam produced due to the oxidation heat source.

The Peak Cladding Temperature (PCT, selected across the whole core), is an indicator of the core temperature and state (Figure 5). We can observe that the PCT increase starts at about 8h into the accident, when water level reaches half of the core, with a rate of about 100 K/h. The temperature increase is caused

by the decrease in the heat transfer being a results of water level drop, removal of liquid convective heat transfer and reduced water steaming (Figure 5).

The increasing temperature at about 13 hours reaches limit of violent exothermal oxidation reaction, mostly in the upper part of the core (Figure 5). The oxidation occurs between zirconium and steam but also between steel components and steam. Reactions produce hydrogen (Figure 6, Left) and high oxidation heat (Figure 6, Right). Temperature and oxidation rate peak, for the studied cases, occurs between 13-15h, and it is a short event. After the peak, there is a drop in temperature (Figure 5) and it is due to termination of the violent oxidation. A large portion of the zirconium at two upper core levels is oxidized. After the peak, the PCT reaches a plateau with values over 1500K at the top of the core and even due to relatively high temperature oxidation is not commencing due to lack of zirconium. The bottom core levels have lower temperatures and unoxidized zirconium. It can be observed that the oxidation is not fully stopped, it has non-violent intensity, and lasts for several hours - between 15h-23h (Figure 6). It can be considered as the second oxidation phase. Cumulatively it produces up to 25% of the hydrogen and mostly due to zirconium (Figure 6-Figure 8). Thanks to the efficient core cooling, there is no temperature escalation. The heat removal is due to the steam natural circulation and heat transfer to the barrel which keep the core in thermal quasi-equilibrium. The hydrogen produced is not considered as a threat for safety as long there is no air ingress. In invastigated cases the atmosphere of CPV consist of steam and Hydrogen thus, combustion of H₂ was not considered.

Figure 5. Peak Cladding Temperatures.

Figure 6. Left - Total hydrogen production due to oxidation in the core. Right - Total oxidation heat generation rate.

After the full core uncover (>20h), and when the water level decreases below the bottom part of the lower support plate, enhanced natural circulation is established. It introduces new flow path for gases and additional heat removal mechanism. However, lack of water reduces heat transfer by steam production and convection by direct contact of water with bottom portion of the core. New convection path increases steam

flow, leads to increased oxidation of the cladding and a third oxidation phase with a minor peak in some studied cases. It is non-violent and coincident with temperature increase (Figure 5-Figure 8). When the reaction ceases, is followed by a temperature drop to the PCT level of 1000K, which stays constant till the end of calculations.

Figure 7. Hydrogen production: Left - due to the zirconium (ZR) oxidation. Right - due to the steel (SS) oxidation.

Figure 8. Left - Mass of the zirconium di-oxide (ZRO2). Right - Mass of steel oxide (SSOX).

Figure 9. Fraction of the fuel that is no longer intact due to loss of support, liquefaction or melting (COR-DAMAGE variable).

Zirconium is responsible for more than 70% of the produced hydrogen (Figure 7). The mass of zirconium oxide and steel (components) oxide is presented in Figure 8. It was estimated that for studied cases maximum possible zirconium oxide mass is about 3250 kg, hence large portion of it oxidized (40-60%). For steel, maximum oxide mass is over 14000 kg and only small portion oxidized (1.5-6%). We can observe

that oxidation for both steel and zirconium is following the temperature increase trends as expected (Figure 5-Figure 7).

The heat production rate (Figure 6, right) is larger than the steam/water is able to extract, at least locally and temporarily during the first oxidation phase, which is followed by temperature escalation up to the point of degradation (Figure 9). Most of the debris consist of a few hundred kilograms of AIC control poison material collected on the core plate. This is due to low degradation temperature of AIC alloy. Measuring the core damage with COR-DAMAGE variable, it can be observed that only small portion of the fuel lost its integrity in the all studied cases. A relatively large portion of cladding oxidized but the fuel stayed intact with oxidized cladding.

5.3. Comparison of the sensitivity cases

Comparing sensitivity cases it can be observed that the studied parameters have impact onto RPV and CPV pressures (Figure 3). These pressures basically follow the hydrogen production trends, as this non-condensable introduces non-negligible partial pressure (Figure 6). The most significant hydrogen production was observed in SA3, and the lowest in SA7; the same observation is for the pressure predictions. The water level in the RPV shows minor differences (Figure 4) with extreme cases SA3 and SA7, which reach BAF at 20h and 22h.

The PCT predictions (Figure 5) for different cases also follow the oxidation trend. In all cases, we can observe that the first temperature peak occurs in the interval 13-15h when half of the core is uncovered and it is the time of the first oxidation phase when the top of the core is oxidized. During the first phase most of the hydrogen was produced. The SA3 is an extreme case, which in fact has a very short PCT peak at 15h and the whole oxidation is much slower than in other cases.

Studying oxidation results we can propose three groups of results (Figure 6 Left and Figure 7 Left). The first group includes cases SA0, SA1, SA2, SA4, SA9, SA10, for which the first strong oxidation phase produces about 50 kg of hydrogen. Immediately, the second phase starts with slower oxidation or no-oxidation at all. Then during the third phase, when core is fully uncovered, there is a short additional zirconium oxidation. Within this group, it is also observed that in terms of hydrogen production and temperatures, cases SA1 and SA2 are very similar because change in SG heat transfer has minor impact on the total H₂ evolution, as DHRS is unavailable in the studied scenario.

Due to similar zirconium oxidation pattern, SA9 is also included in the first group but it is slightly different than other cases. In spite of having similar total hydrogen production it has the lowest steel oxidation among all cases (only 7 kg) but larger zirconium oxidation among its group (Figure 7). The SA9 has low radial and axial heat exchange factors equal to 0.1 (Table I), which is currently suggested MELCOR best practice value [11]. It is characterized by the largest core degradation, which is three time larger than SA0 (Figure 9). For this case, the PCT increase rate is the highest during the first oxidation, and the temperature is higher for longer than for other cases (Figure 5). Also during the third oxidation phase it is characterized by the highest temperature peak (~1700K).

The second group are cases with reduced oxidation during the first temperature peak (SA5, SA6, SA7) between 13-15h (Figure 6-8). Cumulative hydrogen production reaches about 40 kg. The second phase lasts about 10h with continuous slow production of hydrogen until the end of core uncovering with no evident third oxidation phase. These cases have modified heat transfer path with COR_HTR field, which in principle allows for better heat removal from the core during that phase and during the first escalation phase the production is not as large as in the first group. In effect during the second phase, there is unoxidized material, which slowly oxidizes during the second phase.

The third group has one case, i.e. SA3, it that shows distinct behavior with slower progression rate. For this case the first oxidation phase is very long as it lasts 7 hours. It has the highest observed hydrogen generation ~ 85 kg, and the largest steel oxidation. This case has significantly increased radiative exchange factor, which improves core heat extraction. It has the highest steel oxidation but the lowest zirconium oxidation, and there is no further progression of the event after the first temperature excursion (Figure 5 and Figure 6). This case has no second oxidation phase and only the third oxidation phase is present. It is worth to note that, the steel oxidation parabolic kinetics becomes stronger than zirconium kinetics above 1400K for MELCOR default setup, but zirconium is more accessible to steam due to larger surface area for reaction. For SA3, due to longer exposure time for higher temperature the reaction can develop and produce relatively more hydrogen when steam reacts with steel than for other cases.

What is significant, no massive core collapse was observed – there was no case of MELCOR COR ring collapse. In the Figure 9 it can be observed that only small fraction of the core collapsed for all cases. Where the SA3 is close to zero core damage and SA9 has the largest damage. SA3 has very slow accident progression and it allows the core to be effectively cooled and avoid collapse. What was also observed, for the SA3, is that there is slightly less core blockage, especially at the core plate (when considering core void fraction), which is a possible reason of more easy steam access to the core and larger hydrogen production. Another reason and observation is the fact that the lower plenum liquid temperature is larger than for other cases (see Figure 10). In effect, there is more steaming, and steam leaving lower plenum can have a higher temperature in the core and can eventually lead to more intensive oxidation. It can also eventually be linked with heat transfer from the RPV to the CPV but these effects demands further investigation.

Figure 10. Coolant temperature in the Lower Plenum (LP).

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the MELCOR 2.2 model of one of the generic iPWR designs considered in the SASPAM-SA project was developed, presented and tested. Simulations for unmitigated RVV-LOCA scenario were performed. The preliminary parametric sensitivity analysis for selected core heat transfer parameters was prepared.

It can be concluded that the studied parameters have an impact on the simulated accident progression of the core. The progression can to some extent be measured with hydrogen production and core collapse, which are driven by the core temperatures, water levels and heat removal capacity. An interesting observation is the phenomenon of increased natural convection after the water level drops below the core plate, due to the opening of the flow path for gases from downcomer to the core. Among studied parameters, the most significant impact was observed for the radial and axial radiative heat exchange factors. The SA3 case with increased factors has the slowest progression due to higher heat removal as opposed to SA9 with decreased factors, which has relatively the highest degradation of the analysed cases. The SA3 case presents an interesting behavior, in that despite the slower progression, the highest quantity of hydrogen is produced.

It is likely due to less blockages and more uniform heat distribution in the core. Conversely, SA9 with highest core degradation has rather low hydrogen production. In all cases, no core collapse was observed in spite of significant cladding oxidation as between 40–60% of available zirconium oxidized. No significant mass of material was relocated to the lower plenum and most debris consisted of control rod material collected on the core plate. For future work, it is recommended to review and extend the list of parameters in Table I and especially to investigate parameters related to the core collapse.

These preliminary outcomes show non-usual abilities of SMRs to withstand extreme sequences. Results are counterintuitive because typically for large PWR, large oxidation is coincident with core collapse and further meltdown – especially if there is no core reflooding as in the unmitigated LOCA. For the studied design, the heat transfer to the CPV and then to RP and also lower decay heat, lower power-to-volume ratio, and other design features avoid core meltdown in almost all the investigated cases in the studied time span.

This work presents preliminary results and it is a first step in an effort to identify significant parameters and recommended MELCOR modelling practices for Uncertainty Quantification of severe accident analysis of LW-SMRs. Presented outcomes can be useful in the discussion about accident management strategies in iPWR type SMRs.

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Credit authorship contribution statement

M. Malicki: Methodology, Calculations, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - original draft, Visualization, Validation. P. Darnowski: Investigation, Visualization, Validation, Writing - original draft, T. Lind: Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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